

Progress on the commissioning of the Iseult 11.7T whole-body MRI: first images

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Synopsis: The Iseult project started in 2001 and is a collaborative effort involving CEA and the University of Freiburg in academics, Guerbet, Siemens Healthineers and Bruker Biospin as industrial partners. One central aspect of the project has been the design by CEA of a whole-body magnet of 11.7T field strength with a 90-cm wide bore. After nearly 20 years of research and development, prototyping, integration and tests, first images have been acquired with this unique MRI scanner. Some key validation results are presented here.

Purpose: MRI at ultra-high field (UHF) offers great promises in SNR and CNR and has fueled the race to achieve ever higher fields, the highest field used on humans to date being 10.5T at the University of Minnesota (CMRR). With higher fields however come greater challenges (e.g. field homogeneity and stability) which must be overcome to enable proper exploitation. Here we review the key results of the tests performed in the last year to finalize the commissioning of this unique 11.7T whole-body MRI scanner¹, and we present its first high resolution images acquired on a pumpkin and on an ex-vivo brain.

Methods: The main superconducting coil of the Iseult magnet is made of NbTi and is immersed into a 7000-liter He vessel at a temperature of 1.8 K (below the 2.17 K transition from liquid to superfluid He). Following a double pancake design, it sustains a current of 1483 A and has an inductance of 308 H, allowing to ramp-up the field from 0 to 11.7T in approximately 5 hours. This magnet is actively shielded by two 5-m diameter superconducting coils also immersed in superfluid He. The whole magnet assembly weighs 132 tons with external diameter and length of 5 m. After the cool down of the magnet and the first ramp-up at 11.7T in 2019, the imaging equipment (of the MAGNETOM 11.7T MRI series) has been integrated around the magnet. Gradient coil-magnet interaction tests were performed at 3T, 7T, 10.2T and 11.7T, the gradient being the Siemens Healthineers SC72 whole-body gradient. They included acoustics, vibration and power deposition measurements during variable speed frequency sweeps of the three gradient coils independently. Figure 1 reports some vibration data measured on the gradient, the lead tube (designed by CEA to screen gradient-magnet interactions at specific frequencies²) and the magnet cryostat. Temporal field stability (spec of 0.05 ppm/hour max at rest) was measured at 11.7T with an FID sequence over 14 hours on a phantom. The External Interference Shield (EIS) designed to screen external field perturbations was tested with a Skope (Skope MRT, Zurich, Switzerland) field camera with measurements performed at an intermediate field of 7T every 105 ms while a bus was driving on the road nearby. Field homogeneity (spec of 0.5 ppm peak-to-peak over the surface of a 22 cm diameter sphere with passive and cryo shimming only) was mapped by a Metrolab (Metrolab, Geneva, Switzerland) field camera. Tune-up and Quality Assessment of the imaging equipment, in quadrature

mode only for the moment, was performed by Siemens Healthineers with support of CEA. First images were acquired on a pumpkin and an ex-vivo brain using a Gradient Echo sequence with a 0.4 mm isotropic spatial resolution (TR=20 ms, TE = 1.82/2.5 ms, Matrix = 512 × 512 × 448, 4 NEX, TA = 5 H 05 min), using the single channel service quadrature coil (QED) delivered by Siemens Healthineers.

Results: Field stability measurement is shown in Fig. 2a revealing a fluctuation of less than 0.01 ppm over 14 hours. The EIS also reduces by 10 fold the field disturbance caused by a bus driving on the road 50 m from the magnet (Fig. 2b). Field homogeneity relies on passive shim iron (optimized schematics of Al/iron blocks), cryoshims and the Siemens Healthineers active shim. The last measurement returns a peak-to-peak variation of 0.88 ppm and a RMS deviation of 0.15 ppm with the passive and (partial) cryo shim only (Fig. 3), the nominal frequency being 499.415 MHz. Despite a severe but expected³ RF field inhomogeneity at 500 MHz with a quadrature coil, these experimental conditions led to the visualization of exquisite details on high spatial resolution images of the pumpkin (e.g. vegetal fibers) and of the ex-vivo brain (e.g. internal structure of the thalamus), thus validating up to this stage the commissioning of the 11.7T Clinical MRI system.

Discussion and conclusion: The results reported in this work reflect and validate the research and developments performed at CEA for nearly 20 years and now make MRI at 11.7T and with a 90 cm diameter bore a reality. The safety assessment of this new medical device will be started soon to seek authorization to scan human volunteers. Parallel transmission also will be deployed in the near future to mitigate the RF field inhomogeneity problem. Small refinements on the passive shim configuration are also needed to reach the final specifications.

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Figure 1. Acceleration data (Y axis example) measured at 7T, 10.2T and 11.7T. Measurements were performed with accelerometers placed on the cryostat (left), lead tube (middle) and gradient (right) with nominal gradient strength of 1 mT/m on the Y axis. Results were normalized by field strength to underline the evolution with B_0 . The measurements on the gradient (right) illustrate some vibrations evolving less quickly than with B_0 at some frequencies.

The other plots show very different spectra versus B_0 field and indicate significant changes in gradient-magnet interactions.

Figure 2. Field stability and External Interference Shield (EIS) results. a) Field stability (in ppb) measured with an FID every 6 s for 14 hours on a phantom. b) The EIS on greatly reduces the field disturbance caused by a bus driving on a road nearby.

Figure 3. Field homogeneity results at 11.7T. a) Current Iron shim configuration (inner layer). Black and white boxes indicate iron and aluminum respectively. The green and red contours highlight the changes from the previous shim iteration to the next. b) Current field offset obtained with passive shim only, on the surface of a sphere of 22 cm diameter. Homogeneity over the sphere surface is 0.88 ppm pk-to-pk (RMS = 0.15 ppm).

Figure 4. First images acquired on a pumpkin and on an ex-vivo brain at 11.7T. Top row, from left to right: shaded surface display, axial, sagittal and coronal views. Acquisition was performed with a birdcage service coil and with a 3D GRE sequence at 0.4 mm isotropic resolution. Bottom row: axial views of the ex-vivo brain acquisition (0.4 mm isotropic resolution). The B_1^+ field inhomogeneity of the single channel birdcage coil is visible with dark shades.